

Conservation of Structural Ironwork from a Large Downdraft Kiln at the Former Western Clay Manufacturing Company site in Helena, Montana, USA

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The Western Clay Manufacturing Company site in Helena, Montana is a large brick and tile manufacturing site founded in the 1880's. Under the leadership of its owners, Charles Bray and his son, Archie Bray, Sr., Western Clay became Montana's premiere brick and hollow clay tile manufacturing plant by the early 20th Century. The site closed in 1961 and is now home to the internationally recognized Archie Bray Foundation for the Ceramic Arts (ABF). Listed on the National Register of Historic Places, the site is a rare historical and industrial landscape, retaining many of its original structures including five beehive (downdraft) kilns measuring 35 feet (10.6 meters) in diameter and 20 feet (6 meters) in height, and associated kiln sheds, tools, molds and large-scale machinery.

In 2011, the ABF and the Montana Preservation Alliance (MPA) formed an initial partnership to advocate for the protection of the site. Further collaboration was initiated in 2011 with the Architectural Conservation Laboratory of the University of Pennsylvania's School of Design to develop a program for preservation and interpretation of the site.

Within this framework, conservation of metalwork from Kiln No. 7, the most intact and well preserved of five surviving large, composite, kilns began. In 2013, the authors began a program to conserve the historic metalwork of Kiln No. 7, alongside efforts by students from the program in Historic Preservation at the University of Pennsylvania's School of Design to stabilize the historic masonry of the kiln. This presentation describes conservation efforts to conserve the historic metalwork of the kiln which included structural metal components such as seven iron bands that encircle or partially encircle the kiln, two iron doorways and associated bands on either side of the kiln, fireboxes and associated gas valves and burners, and infrastructure from a later installed gas system.

Conservation efforts focused on preserving significance and original fabric with sustainable approaches that emphasized long-term preservation and management by non-conservators. A major challenge of the project was dealing with large-scale, composite structures in situ, the proximity of the metal to salt-laden masonry from the firing of salt-glazed ceramics resulting in severe corrosion, and the harsh environment of Montana. Treatment included a number of exposure tests to determine an appropriate final coating, removal of thick corrosion layers and desalination to reduce salt levels, both of which were performed in situ, and securing the loose bands to the kiln.